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Project Coordinator: Joakim Dillner

Organisation: KI

E-mail: Joakim.Dillner@ki.se

Work Package 6

Informatics platform and Knowledge Engine (PaaS, SaaS)

Work package Leader: Jim Dowling

Organisation: Logical Clocks AB

E-Mail: jim@logicalclocks.com

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Executive Summary

This document provides a full view of the capabilities of the Knowledge Engine within the Human Exposome Assessment Platform (HEAP). The HEAP software platform is built on top of the open-source Hopsworks platform. This document describes the improvements to the Knowledge Engine in Hopsworks (scalable and secure data storage, querying, and annotation) as well as the steps done and planned to implement all the partner pipelines into the HEAP platform. The goal is for the pipelines to fully utilise the benefits of horizontal scaling and sharing of data and code as some of the base qualities of the platform. The implementation presented in this document is coordinated with work package 3 - Large sample cohorts from population-based interventions, work package 4 - Consumer exposure monitoring system, work package 8 - Epigenomics Analysis, and work package 9 - Metagenomic analysis.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose

This document provides guidance for the development of Data Analysis and Machine Learning Pipelines through the use of the Data Analytics and Machine Learning (ML) capabilities of the Knowledge Engine implemented through the HEAP Hopsworks platform. This document describes the technical architecture, data flow, data analysis, and associated metadata of the HEAP pipelines.

1.2 Overview

This document presents improvements to the HEAP Hopsworks platform that have been produced from the following ongoing or completed Tasks.

- As part of **Task 6.2: Implementation of the HEAP integrated data model in Hopsworks** there are improvements to the metadata layer as well as the provenance and activity tracking mechanisms.
- As part of **Task 6.3: Data Warehousing**, there are several developments related to the storage and querying of data where we improved storage with Hudi support and added mutual TLS support for Hive, integrating these improvements in the Feature Store capabilities.
- As part of **Task 6.5: Deep learning on HEAP data** work has been done to integrate the model serving in some of the HEAP pipelines. We have further worked on improving the general performance and usage of the model registry and model serving modules.
- As part of **Task 6.6 Implement in Hopsworks of advanced statistics for optimisation of complex models** we have integrated multi-tenant RStudio support into the HEAP platform.

Additionally, this document describes the collaboration with work package 3 - Large sample cohorts from population-based interventions, work package 4 - Consumer exposure monitoring system, work package 8 - Epigenomics Analysis, and work package 9 - Metagenomic analysis to implement their existing pipelines

with the analysis and machine learning tools and capabilities of the HEAP Hopsworks platform.

We aim to provide a system for collecting, managing, sharing, and ultimately analysing exposome-related data, as defined in the project proposal. The Knowledge Engine ensures that access to sensitive data is according to the permissions set. We still strive to encourage collaboration through sharing of data, once again, if the permissions are correctly adhered to.

Key aspects facilitated by the Knowledge Engine are:

- projects as a shared workspace to enable collaboration for data scientists
- a feature store for curating, storing, sharing and discovering helpful features
- multiple model training framework support together with provenance information for each exploration of experiments
- a model registry for storing, sharing, serving and monitoring of models
- a scalable and consistent metadata layer
- user-definable tags as flexible, structured metadata

All the code related to the HEAP platform will be part of the HEAP-EXPOSOME organisation on Github: <https://github.com/HEAP-EXPOSOME>.

1.3 Structure of the document

The structure of the document is as follows:

- **Chapter 1** (this chapter) introduces the document, its purpose and a list of acronyms and abbreviations.
- **Chapter 2** introduces the improvements to the Knowledge Engine, Hopsworks platform compared to the capabilities presented in deliverable 6.1.
- **Chapter 3** provides a bigger integration work, requested by our partners for a great improvement in the development of their pipelines on the HEAP

Hopsworks platform.

- **Chapter 4** provides a description of the partner pipelines with an emphasis on the systems, data analysis and machine learning parts. We also provide an extended description of the prototype HPV-meta pipeline where extensive work was put to get the whole pipeline implemented early in the HEAP Hopsworks platform to be used as a guideline by the other partners.
- **Chapter 5** describes a recent workshop where the main goal was to present the ready pipeline as an example of how to structure and develop a pipeline in the HEAP BYOD Hopsworks platform. The workshop also explored how the pipeline can be easily applied to data coming from other partners and thus enabling sharing of data, code, and workflows. All new capabilities of the platform were also presented during the workshop with the goal of collecting feedback to further improve the functionality of the platform.

2. Hopsworks as a Data Warehouse

Figure 1: Architecture overview of HEAP Hopsworks platform

Hopsworks, an open-source platform, provides a robust and flexible architecture through the integration of various services used in the design, development and operations of large-scale data analytics and machine learning pipelines. An overview of the HEAP platform, built on Hopworks, is shown in Fig. 1.

The platform provides a large-scale distributed file system (HopsFS) that can scale up to petabytes of data. The RonDB database provides low latency and high throughput access to data that can be made highly available through replication. In HEAP, we required the storage of tabular data that can scale up to petabytes in size, and we worked on extending support for Apache Hive and Apache Hudi to provide scalable tabular (or database) storage capabilities.

Computation can be run on the HEAP Hopsworks platform either as experimental notebooks used for data and computation exploration or as schedulable jobs which can be configured in complex workflows. The HEAP Hopsworks platform supports state-of-the-art processing frameworks such as Spark and Flink. Most popular machine learning libraries such as Tensorflow, Scikit-Learn and PyTorch come pre-installed so that users can easily set up the correct dependencies. Of course, Python computation is a first-level citizen in Hopsworks, and the Python environment is fully customisable by the user. Monitoring of computation, platform operation, and full-text search of files through metadata is performed with the aid of the OpenSearch stack, Filebeat and Prometheus. The Hopsworks Feature Store and Model Registry provide the backbone for the whole data analysis and machine learning design, development, and operations.

2.1 Secure Hive on Hopsworks

Hopsworks implements a secure data warehouse platform using several open-source frameworks, including Apache Hive¹, Apache Hudi², and HopsFS³. Hopsworks is built on a project-based multi-tenant security model, where each user has a different identity for every project where they have membership. This way, when a user uses one of Hopsworks services (such as HopsFS or Kafka) inside a given project, the user can only access those assets (files, topics, tables, indexes) included inside that same project. The user can only run a job that reads/writes assets that are in other projects if explicit permission is given to share that asset across project boundaries.

In this deliverable, we added support to Hive as a project level multi-tenant service, see Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Hopsworks Project-based Multi-tenancy

¹ Apache Hive website <https://hive.apache.org/>

² Apache Hudi website <https://hudi.apache.org/>

³ HopsFS - <https://www.usenix.org/conference/fast17/technical-sessions/presentation/niazi>

Figure 3: Services in Hopsworks implementing Project-User ID

Apache Hive Server2 is the SQL API for Hive, enabling clients to send SQL queries to Hive for large scale data warehousing operations. Open-source Hive Server2 supports TLS for secure communications, but not mutual TLS for client authentication. In Fig. 4, we can see the changes we made to Apache Hive Server2 to implement support for mutual TLS in Hopsworks. We made similar changes to the Hive Metastore to also support mutual TLS.

Figure 4: Hive on Hudi/HopsFS in Hopsworks

With support for mutual-TLS enabled Hive, the user can use Hive in Jupyter notebooks using either the PyHive library or using Jupyter magics as shown in Fig. 5 below.

```
%reload_ext sql
from hops import hive
hive.setup_hive_connection()
```

Load Data into an External table

Let's first create a Hive external and let's point the table to the just created dataset. In the query below you should replace [Projectname] with your project name.

The %%sql magic allows you to write HiveQL and execute the query against the HiveServer.

```
%%sql
CREATE EXTERNAL TABLE sacramento_properties_ext(
  street string,
  city string,
  zip int,
  state string,
  beds int,
  baths int,
  sq_ft float,
  sales_type string,
  sale_date string,
  price float,
  latitude float,
  longitude float)
ROW FORMAT DELIMITED
FIELDS TERMINATED BY ','
LOCATION '/Projects/[Projectname]/RawData'
```

Figure 5: You can use Hive SQL from a Jupyter Notebook in Hopsworks. First, you establish a mutual TLS connection using `hive.setup_hive_connection()`, then you can send SQL queries to Hive Server 2 that executes them in the cluster.

2.2 Hudi on Hopsworks

Apache Hudi (Hadoop Upserts Deletes and Incrementals) can be termed as a streaming data lake platform. It combines the core functionalities of a data warehouse into a data lake. It incorporates support for several tools out of the box and primarily suits users on Apache Spark and Apache Flink. Hudi also makes it possible to build efficient incremental batch pipelines such as ingestion, ETL, etc. along with streaming ingestion. In Hopsworks, we can store data in Hudi tables and query them in Hive, Spark, and Flink. In this deliverable, we made Hudi the defacto tabular file format for tabular data stored in Hopsworks that is queryable by Spark or Hive clients.

2.2.1 Data structure in Hudi

In principle, Hudi relies on data, indexes, and metadata as its core components. In this section we provide a high-level introduction to data management in Hudi.

Figure 6: Data structure of Hudi; [Source: Zangis, R. 2022]

Hudi was originally designed to work using the Hive table format, which was the industry standard. However, it could not handle the workloads which Hudi was proposed for. Therefore, a new table format was developed for Hudi. Hudi table format consists of a file layout of the table, the table's schema, and metadata tracking changes to the table. The format internally consists of multiple file formats which are used to store data in Hudi. An overview of the data structure of the table format is shown in Fig. 6. The data structure can be classified into below files:

1. **Base file:** Stores data after compaction, typically in a parquet file. The contents of a base file can be further subdivided into three distinct parts:
 - a. metadata
 - b. data
 - c. Additional metadata

Hudi Parquet file

commit_time	...	file_name	Col 1	...	Col N
commit_time	...	file_name	Col 1	...	Col N
...
Parquet footer					

Figure 7: Hudi base file parts (orange = row metadata, red = data, blue = footer); [Source: Zangis, R. 2022]

Fig. 7 displays this information with different colors identifying the separate parts (orange = row metadata, red = data, blue = footer). The ‘Hudi skeleton’ comprises metadata and data. It is essential for supporting Hudi primitives (upserts and incremental pulls).

2. **File slice:** It represents a state of a set of records at a given time, which includes the base file and associated delta logs (change logs)
3. **File group:** Pre-defined number of file slices identified by a “file-id”
4. **Partition:** Set of file groups with similar characteristics. This allows a table to have multiple partitions which are saved as folders in the base path.

One of the important benefits of this format is that a read/write transaction on a single entry of table does not need an operation on the entire data set, significantly reducing the overall amount of I/O transactions.

2.3 Custom Metadata and Search

As part of tasks 6.2 and 6.4 we have improved the metadata and search capabilities of the HEAP Hopsworks platform. As reported in deliverable 6.1 HEAP Data Warehouse, users can define and attach custom metadata to files. This metadata can be in the form of key/value pairs and they are called tags, or in the form of key only, in which case they are called keywords. A tag value is defined as a schematized json and follows the rules of json schemas with the reference as <https://json-schema.org>. A new UI is provided so that it is easier to define tag schemas and later attach tag values to values.

Hopsworks also supports free text search for machine learning artifacts:

- features
- feature groups
- feature views
- training datasets

and soon to include:

- experiments
- models
- deployments

Search uses the title, description, components, and tags for the free text search capabilities. To keep this functionality up to date, we have switched from Elasticsearch 7.2.0 to the new open-source search engine OpenSearch version 1.3.6. Opensearch is an open-source fork of Elasticsearch 7.10.2, since Elasticsearch became a closed-source platform as of version 7.10. We have thus upgraded the whole ELK stack to an open-source alternative. As part of this upgrade, we also migrated from Kibana to OpenSearch Dashboards. This was a significant amount of work that necessitated rewriting large portions of the Hopsworks platform.

2.4 Provenance

Hopsworks helps you track the relations between different artifacts involved in the machine learning pipelines. Artifacts currently tracked by provenance are:

- feature groups - be it cached, streaming or external feature groups
- feature views
- training datasets
- models
- experiments

A **feature** is just a variable with predictive power for a machine learning problem or task. A **feature group** is a table of features where each feature group has a primary key and optionally an event time column and a partition key. You can create further feature groups by joining, filtering, or performing any kind of custom transformation on existing features. This process to derive new feature groups can be tracked in explicit provenance by marking the parent feature groups when you create a new feature group. This chain of derived feature groups can be arbitrarily long, and the provenance graph is there to show this chain to you, up to the raw, initial data.

A **feature view** is a logical view over a set of features that may come from different feature groups. The feature view is a representation used for a machine learning model in the feature store. It is used to create training data for the model training, as well as retrieving the feature vectors for operational models.

Training of models is done through experiments. Experiments and models are stored in the model registry.

When deriving feature groups, due to the fact that a spark or pandas data frame can be derived from arbitrary computation, we need to manually set the parent feature groups at creation time. Feature views, training datasets, models and experiments are stricter, and the library knows exactly the parents or input data.

Through the provenance API you can see:

- **from a feature group:**
 - what feature groups were used to generate it.
 - what feature groups were generated using this feature group.
 - what feature views were generated using this feature group.
- **from feature views and training data**
 - what feature groups were used to generate it.
 - training data materialized from this feature view are implicit in the abstraction and do not require provenance to determine them.
 - through the training data artifact, we can also link the feature views with their models.
- **from an experiment:**
 - what model was created
 - what training data was used
- **from a model:**
 - what experiment created it
 - what training data was used to create it

Figure 8: UI representation of the provenance graph

The UI representation of the provenance graph can be seen in Fig. 8. This information is available for all the featurestore artifacts.

As we can see in Fig. 9, provenance can be accessed programmatically in both notebook and normal jobs code.

```

: fg_name = derived_cached_fg_1_name
fg = fs.get_feature_group(fg_name, version=1)
print(fg.get_parent_feature_groups().__str__(indent=2))

{
  "accessible": [
    {
      "feature_store_name": "provenance_featurestore",
      "name": "cached_fg1",
      "version": 1
    }
  ],
  "inaccessible": [],
  "deleted": [
    {
      "feature_store_name": "provenance",
      "name": "cached_fg2",
      "version": 1
    }
  ],
  "faulty": []
}

: fg_name = derived_cached_fg_2_name
fg = fs.get_feature_group(fg_name, version=1)
print(fg.get_generated_feature_views().__str__(indent=2))

{
  "accessible": [
    {
      "feature_store_name": "provenance",
      "name": "feature_view1",
      "version": 1
    }
  ],
  "inaccessible": [],
  "deleted": [],
  "faulty": []
}

: fv_name = fv_1_name
fv = fs.get_feature_view(fv_name, version=1)
print(fv.get_parent_feature_groups().__str__(indent=2))

{
  "accessible": [
    {
      "feature_store_name": "provenance_featurestore",
      "name": "derived_cached_fg2",
      "version": 1
    }
  ],
  "inaccessible": [],
  "deleted": [],
  "faulty": []
}

```

Figure 9: Programmatic access to provenance

3. R-Studio integration

R-Studio⁴ is a popular Integrated Development Environment (IDE) for the R programming language. It is widely used in statistical analysis and in bioinformatics. In this section we describe the architecture of RStudio integration within Hopsworks and the overall functionality.

3.1 Functionality

In this deliverable, we added to HEAP Hopsworks support for integration with RStudio community edition, which is an open-source version. It follows the SaaS (Software-as-a-service) model and easily enables accessing RStudio Server from a web browser. We developed support for multi-tenant RStudio in Hopsworks, allowing multiple users or tenants to access the same software instance.

Figure 10: R-Studio home page in HEAP Hopsworks

R-Studio runs as an on-demand single user instance per project. This means the RStudio server instance runs only when the user needs them and is isolated by project. This makes it resource efficient by not wasting resources when not in use. Furthermore, launching the instance is easily done via the UI as shown in Fig. 10, without the need of the user to configure anything.

⁴ <https://posit.co/products/open-source/rstudio/>

Authentication to the RStudio instance is handled by the username and randomly generated password. The network traffic is also secure as it is encrypted with Transport Layer Security (TLS) protocol⁵. RStudio network traffic is proxied via a HTTP Proxy that we added to Hopsworks using Membrane Service Proxy⁶.

The instance is isolated using Docker⁷ containers. This makes it possible for users to create separate R-Studio instances across different projects, without causing any conflicts between other users or project instances. The base docker image is built on top of the rocker/rstudio⁸ docker image and comes with all the dependencies like system-wide libraries, configuration scripts, etc. baked in.

R-Studio instance supports *HopsFS mount*⁹, which allows securely mounting Hops-FS to local filesystem. This makes it easy for users to work with project resources as though local filesystem in RStudio, improving on sharing resources on project and usability as data can be read/written directly to project space.

Regarding package management, RStudio server uses the default CRAN¹⁰ as the primary package repository. It supports installation of user packages which are specific to a user. System level packages are built directly in the RStudio image. Custom system packages or package repository installation is not yet supported and needs manual procedure from Hopsworks admins.

Fig. 11 shows an example of a web portal of R-Studio server, with the mounted Hops-FS directories highlighted and the portal's secure URL.

⁵ <https://www.cloudflare.com/learning/ssl/transport-layer-security-tls/>

⁶ <https://www.membrane-soa.org/>

⁷ <https://www.docker.com/>

⁸ <https://hub.docker.com/r/rocker/rstudio>

⁹ <https://github.com/logicalclocks/hopsfs-go-mount>

¹⁰ <https://cran.rstudio.com>

Figure 11: R-Studio server portal

RStudio integration was tested thoroughly for different aspects like load up times, concurrency, file system throughput rates, as part of the thesis Chikafa, G. 2021. As per their findings, RStudio server in Hopworks can support up to **44** concurrent user session on a hardware equivalent to 4 n1-standard-8¹¹ worker (8 cores and 30GB RAM of memory) nodes on Google Cloud Platform (GCP).

3.2 Architecture overview

Fig. 12 shows the high-level architecture of RStudio SaaS within Hopworks. The architecture supports multi-tenancy, as all users share the same data layer, application layer and web tier. Additionally, the project provides an encapsulation to group users within the project to share its project specific resources.

¹¹ <https://cloud.google.com/compute/docs/machine-resource>

Figure 12: High level architecture of RStudio SaaS in HEAP Hopsworks; [Source: Chikafa, G. 2021]

The architecture supports on-demand single user RStudio instances per project. This design enables better isolation between instances and provides users with full control over launching and shutting down their instances.

Each RStudio instance is encapsulated as a docker container and runs as a microservice within the Hopsworks host network. This design is also fault tolerant as failure in one instance does not cascade to other instances. As the instances are launched on-demand as per user needs, it improves resource utilization as no resources are kept idle when the instance is not in use. The base docker image for RStudio is built from the `rocker/rstudio`¹² docker image.

The project data is available locally using *HopsFS-mount*. This allows to persist user data into HopsFS even when the containers are shut down and improves on sharing project resources.

¹² <https://hub.docker.com/r/rocker/rstudio>

4. Bioinformatics pipelines on HEAP

4.1 Introduction

Bioinformatics involves analysis of many different data formats with a vast variety of software programs as per the research question at hand. Typically, a study is not just carried out by running a single software application, but rather involves multiple analytical steps with different software applications. This creates a chain of data and programs commonly known as a pipeline. A pipeline in software engineering terms can be explained as a chain of processing or analytical steps carried out in a way such that output of a step is fed to or piped to downstream steps as input, creating a data flow similar to a pipeline. It is a common practice to use pipelines in software engineering. In this context, we use the term pipeline to refer specifically to a bioinformatics pipeline.

In HEAP, partner institutions have developed their own pipelines for their research questions. In the following sections, we take a closer look at the different pipelines being developed by each partner institution. Each pipeline section is further subdivided into sections explaining answers to some of core questions about the pipeline such as:

- What are the datasets being used to analyze by the pipeline? What are its properties?
- What is the research question or aim?
- Overview of the pipeline process. What steps does it carry out?
- Which programming languages or frameworks are being used? What is the computation complexity?
- Are there any scientific studies/results associated with the pipeline?

Thus, these subsections provide an overview of each pipeline by answering above questions. Lastly, we deep dive into one pipeline, HPV-meta, explaining its scientific as well as technical aspects of how we build it using Hopsworks.

4.2 HPV-meta pipeline

4.2.1 Dataset

We used the widely utilized The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA)¹³ dataset.

The dataset included sequencing BAM files (n = 10,908) and a total processed data equivalent to 100 TB

Dataset properties:

We used RNA sequencing files present in TCGA. This is sensitive human sequencing data from the TCGA portal¹⁴ which is publicly available.

4.2.2 Research question

The primary aim is building a pipeline to detect Human Papillomavirus (HPV) to understand HPV association with human cancers, which is important for cervical cancer elimination.

4.2.3 Description

HPV-meta (Human Papillomavirus – meta), is an open-source pipeline that aims to detect HPV presence and transcripts. It can be used both in DNA and RNA sequencing data. It includes all steps for HPV detection (pre-processing, human removal, HPV detection and post-analysis) as well as several features to warn operators for contamination. HPV is not only associated with cervical cancers, but with oro-pharyngeal, anal, penile and vulvar, among others, the pipeline can be used in any of these fields. Furthermore, substituting the database and including any other organism instead of HPV will allow researchers to detect the targeted microorganisms.

¹³ <https://www.cancer.gov/about-nci/organization/ccg/research/structural-genomics/tcga>

¹⁴ <https://portal.gdc.cancer.gov/>

Figure 13: Flowchart of HPV-meta pipeline; Source [Ure A. et.al.]

4.2.4 Overview of processing

An overview of the steps involved in the pipeline is shown in Fig. 13. A brief summary of the workflow in its most important steps is below

1. Preprocessing: We take the raw BAM file as input which is downloaded from TCGA, followed by filter out the human genome related reads. After this, we perform quality checking of reads and filtering out bad quality sequence data
2. Alignments: Next, mapping of sequences to the human reference genome database to achieve high quality alignment is done. Followed by, filtering out non-human reads, and converting to FASTQ format. Next, it performs mapping of reads to HPV reference database using protein alignment
3. Post-processing: Lastly, the results are checked for HPV positivity based on different criterias and variant calling and consensus extraction to generate final results.

4.2.5 Programming language/framework

The pipeline is built using Hopsworks. The code is developed using Jupyter Notebooks using Python and PySpark kernels. It leverages Hopsworks inbuilt framework for parallel process of the data using Apache Spark. The tools or packages used for bioinformatics are open source softwares, predominantly written in C/C++ or Java.

4.2.6 Complexity

The total processing time depends on the number of files and also on the size of an individual file. To process a single file up to 1 GB can take from 10 to 20 minutes whereas the total processing time for complete dataset (n = 10,908) with a volume approximately 90 TB was around 7 days or 168 hours after having parallel computation, which is exponentially faster than linearly processing a single file at a time. The scale of parallelization depends on the number of executor cores which can be launched with the available memory resources in a cluster.

4.2.7 Hardware special requirements

All the tools and programs use CPU for computation without the need for a dedicated GPU. For this reason multiple workers with different numbers of CPU cores were configured for each step of the pipeline.

4.2.8 Summary of results/publications

“HPV-meta” identified HPV transcripts in 488/10,904 specimens and HPV was present in 46/137 organs. Organs with HPV-associated cancers showed the highest number of specimens positive for HPV as expected (cervix uteri (n = 291/309), endometrium (n = 45/561) and tonsils (n = 34/41)), but HPV was also detected in non-HPV associated tumors (e.g. 7/683 cerebrum/brain tumors). All details and results are published in Ure A, et.al 2022

4.2 CSC Microbial pipeline

4.2.1 Dataset

We used colorectal cancer (N= 1600), oral cancer (N=700) and cervical cancer (N=500) metagenome and metatranscriptome datasets including The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA)¹⁵ dataset. The datasets included raw metagenome and meta-transcriptome sequencing FASTQ files.

Dataset properties:

We used both metagenome and meta-transcriptome sequencing files, which is considered sensitive human sequencing data.

4.2.2 Research question

To build a pipeline for comprehensive classification of bacteria, virus, fungi, archaea and protozoan and their functional pathways from metagenome data to understand the highly dynamic human microbiome and its association with colorectal, oral and cervical cancer.

¹⁵ <https://www.cancer.gov/tcga>

4.2.3 High Level architecture diagram of the pipeline

Figure 14: Flowchart of CSC microbial pipeline

4.2.4 Description of pipeline

CSC microbial pipeline, is an open-source pipeline that comprehensively classifies microbial taxa and functional groups. It can be used both in DNA and RNA sequencing data with certain caveats for RNA. The pipeline involves the pre-processing of the raw sequence data, the removal of human derived reads if necessary, the detection of microbial taxa and their functional groups, normalization of the detection and plotting of the compositional diversity and distribution analysis.

4.2.5 Summary of process

An overview of the steps involved in the pipeline is shown in Fig. 14. A concise summary of the workflow in its most important steps is below

- Preprocessing: Single or pair-end FASTQ -files are taken as input files. FASTQ-file is a file type provided by most of current sequencing methodologies (eg. BAM-file can be easily transformed into FASTQ file). FASTQ-files are quality trimmed including

deduplication of likely PCR biases using Cutadapt, Trimmomatic, Picard and BBtools. Only high-quality reads are retained.

- If human reads need to be removed, a user can choose to filter them out using a fast kmer based filtering or mapping of human reads.
- Classification of the high-quality reads: Pre-processed single or paired-end metagenome and meta-transcriptome sequences are classified using two different classifiers: Kraken2 (a k-mer matching algorithm) and MetaPhlan2 (a marker-gene mapping algorithm) with a large curated reference database for bacteria, virus, fungi, protozoa and archaea available (build in December 2022). Microbial functional groups are classified using HUMAnN2 algorithm.
- Quality control and normalization: Output of classification of taxa and functional groups is checked for likely environmental contamination and outliers in the dataset. Further data normalization and transformation for compositional analysis is performed.
- Results estimations and plotting: Distribution of microbial taxa across the dataset and stratified diversity estimations are plotted using R and further used for likely phylogenetic inference of particular microbial taxa.

4.2.6 Language / framework

The pipeline is built using bash, perl and Python scripts. The tools or packages used for the pipeline are open source and detailed setup and descriptions are mostly found in GitHub.

4.2.7 Overview of computation space

The above described pipeline is available in the CSC supercomputing environment (www.csc.fi) under the Linux operating system. The standard resources consist of at least 1TB of storage space and with more than 40 computing nodes and more than 192 GB of RAM for use, in general.

4.2.8 Computation complexity

The total processing time depends not only on the number and size of the fastq -files but also on the analysis type and depth selected for the pipeline. To process a single file with less than 1GB data for microbial taxa classification can take 30 minutes whereas the total processing time for a larger set of data with both microbial taxa and functional group classification can take several days. However, CSC provides a large selection of computational resources and most of the core computations can be parallelized within the CSC computing environment.

4.2.9 Computation hardware

All the tools and programs are available in the CSC High-Performance computing environment and if enough RAM is reserved by the user the pipeline can be executed as a batch job for parallel computing (<https://docs.csc.fi/computing/running/creating-job-scripts-puhti/>)

4.2.10 Scientific studies/publications

This pipeline has been used to validate and analyze microbial taxa from human stool and gut biopsies (Mas-Lloret et al. 2020, Obón-Santacana et al. 2022) and oral/cervical swab samples (Pimenoff et al. 2023).

4.3 European Translational Oncology Prevention and Screening Institute – DNA methylation preprocessing and quality control pipeline (eutopsQC)

4.3.1 Overview

The eutopsQC pipeline prepares raw DNA methylation files (.idat) obtained from the Illumina iScan™ system and performs a quality control and batch effect analysis on them. Individual files, one per sample, are combined and converted into a methylation beta matrix for further downstream analyses, such as the computation of epigenetic age.

The preprocessing pipeline is implemented as a (as of yet private) R package available on github.

4.3.2 Datasets

Raw .idat files are used as input for the preprocessing pipeline. Additionally, a phenotypic file describing other characteristics of the dataset (e.g. processing plate, participant age, beadchip array position) can be provided for batch effect analysis.

4.3.3 Description

The pipeline includes the following steps:

1. **Data loading:** Raw .idat files are loaded using the *minfi* package, and detection p values are extracted.
2. **Low quality sample filtering:** Samples with low fluorescence intensities are filtered out and removed, using an empirically determined threshold of 9.5 (both unmethylated and methylated signal intensity). Additionally, samples flagged by the processing team can be removed. This list must be manually supplied using `path_to_bad_sample_list`. Samples with more than 10% of probes failed will be removed.
3. **Background intensity and dye bias correction:** Background fluorescence intensity and dye bias correction are carried out using the *minfi* R package.
4. **Beta mixture quantile dilation (BMIQ) normalisation:** Probe type bias correction is conducted using the *ChAMP* package. This process is parallelised to speed up the analysis, default is 4 cores.
5. **Filtering of low-quality, cross-reactive, and non-CpG probes:** Probes mapping to the Y chromosome, probes that are cross-reactive or non-CpG probes are removed.

6. **Data imputation:** Any remaining data points with a detection p-value >0.01 are removed and subsequently imputed using the `impute.knn` function from the *impute* R package.
7. **Report and output generation:** Output files (beta matrix, log files) are saved and reports are automatically generated, displaying sample fluorescence intensity, beta distribution, batch effects if pheno file provided).

As inputs, a minimum of the filepath of the raw *idat* files is required. Additional inputs can include a phenotypic file, a list of flagged samples to be removed, cores to be used.

Outputs include the methylation beta matrix, a preprocessing report (.html file with interactive plotly graphs), and log files.

4.3.4 Languages, library, and framework

The preprocessing pipeline is implemented in the R programming environment (currently tested at 4.1.2, but other versions (≥ 3.0) should not cause issues). The pipeline is a custom combination of several published Bioconductor libraries for preprocessing of methylation data, including *minfi*, *ChAMP*, *impute*, and *ENMix*. Due to interdependencies of the abovementioned package, a range of other packages (primarily from Bioconductor), is required.

4.3.5 Complexity

The complexity of the analysis depends on the size of input files and generated intermediary files as part of the pipeline. To save memory, the pipeline offers the option to run the preprocessing pipeline by directory and merge files at the end, but this will increase processing time. For a set of up to approximately 300 samples, the preprocessing pipeline can be easily conducted using 64 GB of memory and 8 cores in 90 minutes.

4.3.6 Hardware special requirements

A minimum of 8 GB RAM is required for processing, more depending on input file number and size, although the option of sequential processing can help to circumvent the requirement for much higher specifications to some extent.

4.3.7 Summary of results/publications

The preprocessing pipeline does not lead to scientific results in itself but is used as the basis for any downstream analyses, as published in several recent publications from our research group (Barrett, James E., Chiara Herzog et. al 2022 / Barrett, James E., Allison Jones 2022/ Barrett, James E., Karin Sundström 2022/ Herzog Chiara et. al 2022)

4.4 Exposome Pipeline

4.4.1 Dataset

We used both DNA and RNA sequenced files from filters collected by a wearable exposometer.

Dataset properties:

We used DNA and RNA sequencing files from previous research. These sequenced reads cover all domains of life, including human, microbial, animals and plants.

4.4.2 Research question

Building a pipeline to identify biological exposome components from samples collected by a wearable exposometer.

Figure 15: Overview of the exposome pipeline

4.4.3 Description

The exposome analysis pipeline, or Universal Fragment Classification (UFC) pipeline, is a collection of scripts in shell and Python. The patented pipeline includes automatically splitting

input for massively parallel database searching and associated output parsing, automatic evaluation of the input and output to see if the results are complete, and a resume option in case where prior searching steps were interrupted due to unforeseen circumstances. Searching tens or hundreds or thousands of contigs of nucleic acids through a massive database is a very time consuming and computing extensive job, therefore careful optimizations need to be done to ensure the running time for each sample is within a reasonable time-frame.

In brief as shown in Fig. 15, sequenced reads will first go through duplication removal and quality check. Then the reads will be mapped to the human reference genome to remove all human reads. Next, de novo assembly is used to assemble reads into contigs to increase the confidence of subsequent classification. The contigs will then be used to query against our custom-made database and taxonomy will be called using Lowest Common Ancestor (LCA) method.

4.4.4 Programming language / framework

The UFC pipeline is a collection of scripts in shell and Python. The tools or packages used for bioinformatics are open source softwares, predominantly written in C/C++ or Java.

4.4.5 Complexity

The total processing time depends on the number of files and size of an individual file. To process a single file, it can take up to 2-3 days. The total time could be reduced after having parallel computation of the blast step, which is the main time-limiting step of the pipeline.

4.4.6 Hardware

All the tools and programs use CPU for computation without the need for a dedicated GPU. Different numbers of CPU cores were configured for each step of the pipeline to provide sufficient computing power.

4.4.7 Summary of results/publications

The pipeline was published in Chao Jiang et. al, 2018 where we analyzed exposure profiles from 15 individuals after collecting up to 2 years of sampling. We identified over 2500 species and 3000 chemical features, demonstrating the most comprehensive human exposome to date. The pipeline also received an international patent Ronald Davis et al. 2022.

4.5 AI-based alignment-free (agnostic) HPV detection pipeline

4.5.1 Dataset

We used the widely utilized The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) dataset¹⁶. The data have been preprocessed with a KI HPV-meta pipeline discussed before and human sequences have already been removed from the input data. Our input data (n = 10,904) were in the format fq.gz.

Dataset properties:

Only 4.5% of samples were HPV-positive as classified with “HPV-meta”. Also, the size of available sequencing files varied, ranging from several MiBs to hundreds of MiBs. The sequences from the biggest files could have easily overwhelmed the sequences coming from the smaller files. Such imbalances in the number of negative and positive samples and size are one of the reasons neural network training may become derailed. To mitigate this, it was decided to use only the smaller files (< 35 MiBs in size) for training and a balanced subset of the TCGA available data. We set the length of the sequences to 80 and complemented shorter sequences with padding to 80 characters. We limited the training instances only to samples biopsied from the endometrium as well as cervix uteri (most of them HPV positive) to provide a similarity on the biological level. These were 159 HPV positive and 159 HPV negative chosen to use for the classifier and split into training, validation and test set in the proportion of 101:29:29.

4.5.2 Research question

AI-based Human Papillomavirus (HPV) classifier to detect HPV-containing samples.

¹⁶ <https://www.cancer.gov/about-nci/organization/ccg/research/structural-genomics/tcga>

Figure 16: Flowchart of AI-based alignment-free (agnostic) HPV detection pipeline

4.5.3 Description of pipeline

AI-based alignment-free (agnostic) HPV detection pipeline is one of the few pipelines applying AI to detect HPV sequences. We have chosen a CNN architecture due to its versatility and acceptable computational times. We obtained a well-performing classifier. By the end of the third epoch 0.8 accuracy was achieved for the test set and 0.81 for the validation set. This does suggest that no overfitting was present. Precision results were, respectively, 0.73 and 0.74. The recall was, respectively, 0.99 and 1. F1 score is thus 0.84 (training set) and 0.85 (validation set).

All subsequences from a given file were labeled according to the value of the `diamond_positivity` metadata field. Thus, it was assumed that all short nucleotide strings in a given file are instances of the same class, either viral or non-viral. Our pipeline uses `fq.gz` files from the TCGA database as entry data and human sequences have already been filtered out.

In the further stages, after changing the labels, the same model can be used for the detection of the samples that progressed into cancer. Further plan is to add a post processing step in terms of Explainable AI (XAI), such as solutions based on GRAD-CAM or SHAP.

4.5.6 Summary of process

An overview of the steps involved in the pipeline is shown in Fig. 16 A brief summary of the workflow in its most important steps is below:

- Prepossessing: Data preprocessing include preparing a generator based on diamond positivity, padding, one hot encoder (changing categorical data into numerical data), selecting the file from cervix uteri and endometrium, filtering out files bigger than 35 MiBs size and splitting the data into a training, validation and testing datasets.
- CNN: The architecture of CNN is presented within Fig. 16 . It contains more than 100,000 training parameters and consists of training, validation and testing steps. Due to the padding, the masking layer was used as CNN's first layer. Whilst dropout layers were included, in the training procedure presented, this regularization method was in fact not used. The dropout rate was set to 0. Hyperparameters can be further optimized and the postprocessing step containing XAI can be added.

4.5.7 Language / framework

The pipeline is built using Hopsworks. The code is developed using Jupyter Notebooks using Python and PySpark kernels. Parallelization of data processing was not necessary however the model training was performed on 1 GPU worker.

4.5.8 Computation complexity

We processed 159 HPV positive and 159 HPV negative samples, totalling 318 samples, without human sequences and with a large sample of >35 MiBs filtered out.

When training the model using the data selected from the dataset, the following parameters were used: *learning rate* = 0.002, *epochs* = 3, *dropout* = 0, *batch size* = 32. Those values were chosen on the basis of earlier experiments using the smaller subsets of the complete dataset. This training took about five days, with ca. 0.24 ms per step. These calculations were quite heavy for

the available CSC cluster and it was unable to sustain calculation speed if other jobs were run at the same time.

4.5.9 Computation hardware

In the next step, we plan to check how our model, learned on the samples without human sequences, will perform on the TCGA files containing human sequences. To do it we need more computational resources, both in terms of CPUs and GPU available. Recently we obtained access to the GPU on Puhti and Mahti supercomputers in CSC. However, we still need a space to store sensitive and non-sensitive data for processing on the Mahti supercomputer as our storage place is located elsewhere.

4.5.10 Scientific studies/publications

The work for training and validation of the model is already published as part of conference paper Mroczek M et. al. 2022. As soon as there will be a possibility to test our model on the TCGA data on the files containing human sequences and given that we reached satisfactory results, we can write up a paper based on the training method. Further, we could work on the paper based on the application of our model to the cancer prediction, however, this project depends strongly on the data availability.

4.6 CPD-enrich pipeline

4.6.1 Dataset

We used following datasets as per the broad category :

- 1) Input Consumer purchase data:
 - a) Simulated consumer data set derived from the *mypurchases* cohort (WP4)
- 2) Enrichment data:
 - a) Product_and_frida_stems dataset
 - b) Openfoodfacts dataset

Dataset properties:

The unique highlights of the dataset properties are as follows:

1. **Consumer purchase dataset** that has a timestamp, *itemname* and an *itemnumber* for each product, and a measure of quantification of items, price etc.
2. **Product_and_frida_stems** dataset contains word stems matching a number of predefined product categories of which the majority are FRIDA data (Fødevaredata ,2022).
3. **Openfoodfacts** dataset contains user generated information on the number of food products sold around the world¹⁷.

4.6.2 Research question

The primary research question is can we improve methods to annotate, enrich and validate products identified using continuously collected consumer data such as electronic receipt

S.

¹⁷ <https://world.openfoodfacts.org/>

Figure 17: Simplified flowchart of CPD-enrich pipeline

4.6.3 Description of pipeline

A key challenge in consumer data research is to move beyond the product names and analysis of a limited number of products, to analysis of all purchased products including information on ingredients, product groups, product type, and category, nutrients, packaging information etc.

The *CPD_enrich* pipeline is a general-purpose enrichment pipeline where products may become enriched using the *itemname* or the *itemnumber*. The *CPD_enrich* enables preprocessing of consumer data and matching by *itemname* and *itemnumber* and allows for validation and quality control of conducted matches. The pipeline may accommodate many different product databases and can easily be adapted to work with other product databases including cosmetics as well.

4.6.4 Summary of process

A high-level overview of the pipeline is shown in Fig. 17. A brief breakdown of the the steps is as follows:

1. Preprocessing

Preprocessing includes the removal of stop words, and abbreviations that may interfere with later regex matching steps. In addition identification information from product names that are of general character, i.e. product weight, volume, origins or type i.e. ecological) are performed and extracted for later use.

2. Regex matching

After preprocessing regex matching is commenced using the dataset *product_and_frida_stems* that contains regular expressions matching more than 1000 mutually exclusive product types. The dataset is designed to work in a matching algorithm that prioritizes stems and selects the *itemnames* best matching the product type and assigns a score indicating the strength of the match. Only products reaching a score above threshold are enriched.

3. Direct matching

Further direct matching based on GTIN13 *itemnumber* is performed for all *itemnumbers* and can be extended to include other product databases using the GTIN 13 standard.

4. Validation

Validation is standard and dataset depicting the greediest matches, ambiguous stems (if any), and products not reaching threshold (unmatched products), etc. are produced enabling quality control. Finally cross validation of select variables found in both enrichment dataset is performed.

4.6.4 Language / framework

The pipeline is built using R and is implemented with the targets package.

The pipeline uses the following additional R-packages:

→ "tidyverse", "janitor", "data.table", "ggplot2", "readr", "knitr", "stringr", "qwraps2", "openxlsx", "readxl", "DBI", "conflicted", "svglite", "DescTools", "wordcloud2", "pacman", "odbc", "bookdown", "lubridate", "psych", "corrplot", "car", "lubridate", "SMLE", "kableExtra", "rsvg", "flextable", "DescTools", "tidyr", "parallel"

4.6.5 Computation complexity

The total processing time depends on the number of files and size of an individual file. For a dataset with approx. 150.000 unique *productname / itemname* combinations runtime is about 1.5 hours on one medium sized CPU.

4.6.6 Computation hardware

The pipeline can run on a single CPU. Multiple workers with different numbers of CPU cores can be configured for each step of the pipeline, and independent steps may run in parallel with the other steps.

4.6.7 Scientific studies/publications

Publications and open-source status is expected to be released during early 2023.

4.7 Extended HPV-meta Pipeline Description

In the era of cervical cancer elimination, accurate and reliable pipelines to detect Human Papillomavirus (HPV) are essential to elucidate and understand HPV associations with human cancers. That is why we designed and validated HPV-meta (Human Papillomavirus – meta), an open-source pipeline that aims to detect HPV presence and transcripts. The pipeline aims to detect HPV in sequencing data and is built using Hopsworks. It can be used both in DNA and RNA sequencing data. End-to-end steps for HPV detection (pre-processing, human removal, HPV detection and post-analysis) are incorporated into the pipeline, as well as several features to warn operators for contamination. As HPV is not only associated with cervical cancers, but with oro-pharyngeal, anal, penile and vulvar, among others, the pipeline can be used in any of these fields. Furthermore, substituting the database and including any other organism instead of HPV will allow researchers to detect the targeted microorganisms. In the following sections, we closely look at each aspect of the pipeline development.

4.7.1 Process

An overview of the steps involved in the pipeline is shown in Fig. 13. Each individual step of the pipeline is described in detail in Table 1.

Figure 18: Flowchart of HPV-meta pipeline; Source [Ure A. et.al.]

Step Nr.	Process	Tool/software	Description
1	Input	Download TCGA BAM file	TCGA bam file
2	Remove human regions	samtools	The TCGA original raw data is presented as BAM files, and alignment was performed against a human reference genome together with some viral sequences. Files contain information about the chromosomes to where they were aligned to, and therefore, as a preliminary step, we created a list of those chromosomes ID and removed the human sequences present in the files that mapped at

			those regions, using samtools.
3	Convert to FASTQ	samtools	The BAM format file is sorted by reads and converted to FASTQ format
4	Quality trimming	trimmomatic	Quality checking and trimming of low quality reads
5	Map reads to human reference	Nextgenmap (NGM)	Aligns reads to a human reference database by NIH
6	Remove human reads	samtools	Filter out unwanted human mapped reads
7	Convert to FASTQ	samtools	Convert SAM format to FASTQ format
8	Diamond HPV	diamond	Protein alignment against HPV reference database
9	HPV positivity filter	Python	This script marks each read for HPV positive or negative based on different metrics
10	Post-processing	Python	This step includes a calculation of the coverage for each sequencing file and reports the total coverage as well as the coverage for each HPV gene. Furthermore, it generates a consensus fasta file for each HPV type classified as positive within a specimen that can be used for contamination inspection and SNP analysis.

Table 1: Steps of HPV-meta pipeline; Source [Ure A. et.al.]

As we can see in Fig. 13 and Table 1, there are a number of steps of processing which need to be run sequentially to get from the raw input to final output. Many of the steps mentioned above, e.g. human reads alignment is computationally heavy. Additionally, the data involved is huge. Such programs are often written in low level languages like C or C++, and even though they compute with fast and efficient algorithms for a single file, they often do not support distributed computing technologies, such as Apache Spark or Hadoop. This becomes the biggest challenge in making such tools scalable for data volumes in giga or terabytes. This downside is

critical for volumes of data similar to TCGA where a single server environment is not feasible no matter what hardware.

Secondly, as there are many tools and software involved, managing these and the members of the project can be cumbersome. Environments would need manual installations and resolving conflicts if any. Sharing the pipelines to other members can be tricky if they do not have the required access privileges.

Conventionally, building such a pipeline would be done through some sort of scripting language, commonly bash scripts. Such scripts lack the ability to monitor the live progress of the pipeline unless a specific mechanism is built. It can be a disadvantage as some of the steps could continue to run for multiple days. Monitoring the progress can be useful as one can take corrective actions if needed.

Hopsworks solves the issues of scalability as we leverage its distributed storage file system (HopsFS) for storing data and support for containerized data-parallel computing applications through Apache Spark to process tera-byte scales of data.

As the project environment is encapsulated, we installed all the programs and tools without causing conflicts to other projects. Since the data and tools can be shared to other members within the project, other members added to the project could collaborate to work the data and the pipeline. This resolved the security issues in access privileges. In the next section, we investigate the technical aspects of developing the pipeline in Hopsworks.

4.7.2 Methods

In this section we describe the technical details of implementation of the pipeline. We look at the data, tools and the methods used in building and running the pipeline.

A. Datasets and tools

We used the widely utilized TCGA dataset. In total, we downloaded 10908 files from a combination of projects within TCGA from its data portal¹⁸. To download the files, we used its GDC data transfer CLI tool¹⁹. A metadata file containing a list of details of the files to be downloaded was first exported from the portal and each file from the list was downloaded at a time in a Jupyter notebook.

We installed the necessary packages and software from within the Project Python installation manager. For software which were not available as part of Conda²⁰ or Python Package Index (PyPI)²¹ with the necessary version, we built the binaries and uploaded them to the project. Below Table 2 gives a list of packages installed.

¹⁸ <https://portal.gdc.cancer.gov/>

¹⁹ https://docs.gdc.cancer.gov/Data_Transfer_Tool/Users_Guide/Getting_Started/

²⁰ <https://docs.conda.io/en/latest/>

²¹ <https://pypi.org/>

Package	Installer	version
nextgenmap	Conda	0.5.5
cutadapt	PyPI	3.5
pysam	PyPI	0.17.0
PyYAML	PyPI	5.4.1
Trimmomatic ²²	manual	0.39
Diamond ²³	manual	2.0.1
Samtools ²⁴	manual	1.12

Table 2: Package installations

Since some of the tools need a reference database file, like a human genome reference, these prerequisite files were uploaded to a dataset in the project. To be precise, the reference databases needed are:

1. HPVproteinsincludingnonoficial_201119.faa (used for HPV protein alignment)²⁵
2. Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.dna.primary_assembly.fa.gz (human reads mapping)²⁶

B. Business logic

Each block/step of the pipeline is split into independent spark jobs running its corresponding program. The coding is done in Jupyter notebooks, mostly using PySpark kernel. Developing with Jupyter makes it easy for interactive programming, documentation, and testing if the code works. Once the notebooks are developed and tested, we created a Hopsworks Job for notebook program to run on the whole batch of data. The general business logic of the process can be broadly divided into following steps:

- Create a list of full HDFS paths of all files for the input folder specified
- Create spark resilient *distributed dataset* (RDD)²⁷ of the list

²² <http://www.usadellab.org/cms/?page=trimmomatic>

²³ <https://github.com/bbuchfink/diamond>

²⁴ <https://www.htslib.org/>

²⁵ <https://pave.niaid.nih.gov/>

²⁶ https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/assembly/GCF_000001405.26/

²⁷ <https://spark.apache.org/docs/latest/rdd-programming-guide.html>

- Create a spark map function on the RDD which will process one file at a time. This function has the business logic necessary to process a file as per the program that needs to be run. The steps within the function can be divided into:
 - Copy the input file from project HDFS to executor local memory
 - run the program command with required arguments as a subprocess in Python. This command is equivalent to running the program through a bash command.
 - copy output files back to output folder in project
- Spark creates the data partitions for the list and applies the map function in parallel on these partitions so that the workload is distributed across the number of executors
- **Configuration file for input arguments**

The parameters and arguments needed for each program are consolidated in a single YAML configuration file. This file also links the corresponding input/output paths for programs creating a chain of data flow necessary for the pipeline. The user must provide the raw input data folder name and the working directory for creating outputs, other parameters are already set with default values. For example, the code snippet below in Table 3 shows the variables for setting the root input and output folder paths.

```
# Dataset for pipelines outputs
OUTPUT_DATASET: Pipeline_outputs/
# Raw Input Dataset hdfs path
INPUT_ROOT_PATH: &INPUT_ROOT_RAW Raw_input/
# Current run working folder. All outputs created under this folder
RUN_FOLDER: run_test
```

Table 3: Example of YAML file for input/output parameters

This allows for parameterization of a lot of program arguments instead of hardcoding them and making it flexible for users to modify them. The path of this YAML file is then passed as an argument to any job before running. To be more specific the arguments to be passed to any job are:

- -s /path/to/settings.yml,
- -i Input dataset HDFS path override (optional),
- -o Output dataset HDFS path override (optional)

The options *-i* and *-o* provide an optional way to override the input and output paths mentioned in the settings file making it more flexible for users to modify it at runtime.

C. Scheduling of jobs

After the jobs were configured for each of the programs, we used Apache Airflow²⁸ which is integrated in Hopsworks to orchestrate the jobs to launch automatically. Fig. 19 and Fig. 20 show examples of the Airflow portal integrated in Hopsworks.

Figure 19: Example Airflow in Hopsworks

Figure 20: Example of pipeline graph in Airflow

With a few modifications to the airflow script, any user within the project can run the same pipeline as per their need. An Airflow pipeline is specific to a user, so they can change the order of jobs described in the pipeline Python script to potentially create a different sequence in the pipeline. For example, in the code snippet image in Table 4, a user should change the *DAG_OWNER*, *PROJECT_NAME* and *DAG_ID* variables to run the pipeline for their project.

²⁸ <https://airflow.apache.org/>

```
# Username in Hopsworks
# Click on Account from the top right drop-down menu
DAG_OWNER = 'username'

## Project name this DAG belongs to
PROJECT_NAME = 'project1'

# Settings file for pipeline arguments
SETTINGS = " -s
hdfs:///Projects/'project1'/Jupyter/Bio_pipeline/settings/settings_t
cga.yml"

# Our DAG
dag = DAG(
    # Arbitrary identifier/name
    dag_id="HPV_meta",
    default_args=args,
    # Run the DAG only one time
    # It can take Cron like expressions
    # E.x. run every 30 minutes: */30 * * * *
    schedule_interval="@once")
```

Table 4: Snippet for airflow script

4.7.3 Scientific findings

“HPV-meta” identified HPV transcripts in 488/10,904 specimens and HPV was present in 46/137 organs. For some cancer forms, like cervical cancers, it is already known that they will regularly contain HPV transcripts from the E6 and E7 viral oncogenes and these cancer forms did serve as a positive control in this project. Organs with HPV-associated cancers showed the highest number of specimens positive for HPV as expected (cervix uteri (n=291/309), endometrium (n=45/561) and tonsils (n=34/41)), but HPV was also detected in non-HPV associated tumours (e.g. 7/683 cerebrum/brain tumours).

To validate the results, we examined all original bam files from the TCGA as they had the HPV mapping information and compared those results with the results from “HPV-meta”. There was almost a 100% agreement (99.98%) with only 2/488 HPV positive samples not reporting the same genotype. The disagreement of one of them (cervical tumour) could be explained due to a multiple infection of 2 genotypes presenting the same number of reads in the same sample. The second disagreement occurred in one ovarian tumour where 2 different non-officially HPVs were reported. While the type detected in the original bam files corresponded to HPV-mCG3 (non-official HPV sequence submitted in 2012), the “HPV-meta” revealed presence of

HPV-mSK041 (non-official HPV sequence submitted in 2018, and therefore not present in the original database). It can be thus confirmed that “HPV-meta” could detect all HPVs with no obstacle.

In conclusion, the “HPV-meta” pipeline has shown to be an open-source pipeline which accurately detects HPV in sequencing data with validated cut-offs. All information and results are published in study Ure A et al. 2022.

The parallel processing of data helped as we could distribute the workload across different executors leading to exponentially faster turnaround times compared to single server setup. Since the pipelines are in a project, it is reusable for other users. We are further improving the pipeline based on the users’ feedback. The code base is available on GitHub at <https://github.com/hpvcenter/HPV-meta.git>

4.7.4 Further work and discussion

HPV meta was designed to be reusable, generic and further developed. As we mentioned before, the pipeline can also be used to detect other metagenomic targets than HPV. Users/researchers have the option to use only a part of the pipeline, as the sequence of jobs can be modified, creating a new pipeline for different input data types. In the BYOD workshop it was discussed and agreed to use the pipeline on FASTQ format input data instead of BAM format as in TCGA dataset. This will make the pipeline even more generic, and any user will be able to use their raw fastq files and run the whole pipeline.

We are now developing more tools to be included in the pipeline. One of them is Kraken2²⁹ which is already under development in Hopsworks (manuscript is on draft status). Kraken2 is a powerful tool for detecting all bacteria, virus, and fungi in the samples. It can be used for metagenomic/metatranscriptomic studies. Adding it to the pre-processing of the HPV-meta pipeline will generate taxonomic classification for any raw bam/fastq file. Another tool that is under development in Hopsworks is the post-analysis for Kraken 2, where R scripts will use the Kraken output to analyze *alpha and beta diversity*, as well as to create an *html* report with all the kraken results. Further tools for machine learning and novel discovery are now being developed with the aim to be also included in the bioinformatics pipeline and hopsworks features.

²⁹ <https://ccb.jhu.edu/software/kraken2/>

5. Bring Your Own Data workshop

In November 2022, we had the second workshop named Bring Your Own Data (BYOD).

Prior to this workshop, there was extended collaborative work to adapt and parallelize the HPV-meta pipeline in order scale on the Hopsworks platform. The purpose of this work was:

- to provide an example of a pipeline adapted for the HEAP Hopsworks platform
- to show the reusability of code by running the same pipeline on other, similar datasets.
- to gather all requirements for the running environments of all HEAP pipelines.

A second goal of the workshop was to introduce RStudio to the partners and include it in the workflow of their pipelines.

5.1 Reusable, Scalable Pipelines

The main goal of the BYOD workshop was to design scalable pipelines that can be reused, with minor configuration changes, on different datasets. So, for example, the HPV pipeline was designed so that it could be easily adapted to other partner's datasets if they adhere to the same interface. For example, in the BYOD workshop it was discussed and agreed to use the pipeline on FASTQ format input data instead of BAM format as in TCGA dataset. This will make the pipeline even more generic, and any user will be able to use their raw fastq files and run the whole pipeline. The pipeline is also split into well-defined staged (jobs) which can also be shared between pipelines.

5.2 RStudio

During the BYOD workshop, RStudio in Hopsworks was tested for developing R projects by different partners. Based on the study, some limitations were highlighted.

One of the most asked for improvement was related to installation of R packages. R packages are split into user level packages and system level packages. While users could install user level packages, the ability to install system level packages is not yet exposed to users as it requires additional privileges. In our case, system packages are baked in during building the docker image for RStudio. As a workaround, such packages can be installed manually by modifying the docker image by Hopsworks admin. Also, there were requests to install additional packages in the base RStudio docker image as any new R project will most likely require these additional libraries.

Based on the feedback from different users at BYOD, we are planning to include investigations into providing custom docker images and/or better support for user library installation in future work.

Furthermore, currently running R programs as jobs in Hopsworks is not supported. This functionality is also being planned to be worked on, which will allow users to run their R scripts directly as Jobs in Hopsworks.

5.3 Model Serving in Hopsworks

As part of task 6.5 we brought improvements to the model registry, created a model servings management module and have developed a Python sdk library, hsml, to interact with the model registry and the model serving management.

Among the model registry improvements, we have worked towards providing an improved, more flexible model metadata. For example, you can now attach the input and output schemas to models as well as attach input examples that can be easily used for a quick testing of a serving of this model.

Among the model serving improvements, we mention upgrading from KFServing to KServe, as well as adding support for serving sklearn model and Python based model through KServe. We added fine-grained support for scalability configuration, allowing us to configure minimum and maximum resources allocation, as well as minimum and maximum number of instances for better scalability support. We also added support for fine-grained configuration of inference batching, such as batch size and max latencies. Performance is important to us, so we added support for low latency inference requests through the Istio Gateway. However, we do not want to reduce security for the sake of performance, so this access uses Hopsworks API keys for authentication.

5.4 Development of HEAP pipelines

There are four major milestones in the implementation of the HEAP Pipelines as presented in Fig. 21.

Figure 21: Designing and Developing the Heap Pipelines

The first milestone which is already achieved is for each pipeline to be implemented on partner infrastructure, even though it could be on a small scale, or the computation might take a very long time.

The second milestone is to take one of the pipelines, in this case the HPV-meta pipeline and bring it to the HEAP Hopsworks platform. This required some changes in code and workflow management but allowed for a high degree of parallelism, allowing us to manage the computation time depending on the available resources. This second milestone was achieved, and the results presented during the 3rd Bring Your Own Data workshop. Both the code and data are present in the platform and the design, development and usage of the pipeline was presented during the workshop with the intent of it being an example and guideline for the other pipelines in the project.

We are currently working in parallel on the other two milestones. The HEAP Hopsworks platform provides great support for collaboration in the form of data, code and workflow sharing and with this in mind we have already started during the workshop the work on running the HPV-meta pipeline on other partner dataset samples. The goal here is to showcase how easy it is to share data and computation within the platform.

The fourth and final goal is to have all the partner pipelines running in the platform and benefiting from the sharing and scaling capabilities of the HEAP Hopsworks platform. Following the second goal of fast pacing one of the pipeline migrations into the HEAP Hopsworks, we are confident that the process as well as the code can be easily used as guideline by the other partners to move their pipeline into the HEAP Hopsworks platform.

Conclusion

In this deliverable, we introduced the work done on D6.2, the HEAP Knowledge Engine. This included work on extending the HEAP Hopsworks platform to support secure, scalable data storage and querying with Hive and Heap. We added processing support through integration of multi-tenant project support for RStudio, along with HopsFS-mount for local file access of data stored in HopsFS. We described the partners' work on Pipelines for HEAP and outlined their progress on integration and scalability on the HEAP platform. We showed how the HPT-meta pipeline was scaled to process hundreds of TBs of data on HEAP Hopsworks. Finally, we summarized the results of our BYOD workshops, where we worked on helping partners to onboard to HEAP Hopsworks and redesign their pipelines for security and scale.

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